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Mathematics: Analysis and Approaches HL

Modelling Orbits

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1 Introduction

This investigation aims to establish a general mathematical model for the motion of two massive objects in a closed three-dimensional space, referred to as the ‘two-body problem’ by astrophysicists. Specifically, the investigation will attempt to create a mathematical function that describes the orbit of the bodies.

To do this, a vector-based approach will be taken, whereby the system will be described in terms of the position vectors of the bodies.

Due to the limitations in our observation abilities, it is difficult to experimentally observe the exact movements of massive objects in space, particularly in the case of distant bodies. For this reason, purely mathematical models of the movements of bodies in space are of significant importance, as our understanding, modelling and prediction of such phenomena must predominantly come from the manipulation and application of known laws of physics.

Orbital mechanics was a topic of particular interest for me in my physics class, and applying ideas of calculus to orbital models—a step beyond the IB Physics course—intrigued me.

2 Newtonian Mechanics

Before creating the model, some fundamental laws of physics must first be understood.

2.1 The Universal Law of Gravitation

Issac Newton’s universal law of gravitation states that the gravitational force of attraction between two objects is proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them.

It is possible to express this law algebraically, where:

1. F is the force of attraction in Newtons
2. G is the gravitational constant ($6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2\text{kg}^{-2}$)
3. m_1 and m_2 are the masses of each bodies 1 and 2 respectively
4. r is the absolute distance between the centres of the two objects

$$F = \frac{Gm_1m_2}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

This force is applied equally to both bodies in the direction of the other body.

2.2 Newton’s Second Law

Newton’s second law of motion states that when a body is acted upon by a force, the rate of change of its momentum with respect to time is equal to the force, where a body’s momentum (p) is the product of its mass (m)

and velocity (v)¹. For an object of **constant mass**, the following manipulation may be performed:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{dp}{dt} \\ \frac{dp}{dt} &= \frac{m(dp)}{dt} = m \frac{dp}{dt} = ma \\ F &= ma \\ a &= \frac{F}{m} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Therefore, for an object of constant mass, when a force is applied to it, the acceleration experienced is equal to the quotient of the force divided by the object's mass.

2.3 Centre of Mass

The centre of mass of a system of bodies is defined as the average position of all bodies, weighted according to their masses.²

2.4 The Two-Body Problem

The scenario that will be explored in this investigation may be described as a closed system of three dimensions containing two objects, each with individual masses and initial velocities.

Following Newton's laws, both objects experience a gravitational force, generating an unequal acceleration inversely proportional to their respective masses in that direction.

3 Solution to the Two-Body Problem

3.1 Establishment of a Centre-of-Mass Coordinate System

By observing a two-body system from an inertial frame of reference (whereby the observer is not subject to any acceleration and so moving at a constant velocity), it is possible to define the positions of each of the bodies as a vector from an origin point. In doing this, the following coordinate diagram may be produced:

¹Britannica. (2023). Newton's laws of motion - Newton's second law: $F = ma$. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/Newtons-laws-of-motion/Newtons-second-law-F-ma>

²Khan Academy. (2018). What is center of mass? Khan Academy. <https://www.khanacademy.org/science/physics/linear-momentum/center-of-mass/a/what-is-center-of-mass>

Figure 1: Coordinate System

In this system, there exists a body of mass of m_1 and position vector of \vec{x}_1 , and another of mass of m_2 and position vector of \vec{x}_2 . The centre of mass for the system is therefore located at the position vector \vec{R} , where:

$$\vec{R} = \frac{1}{m_1 + m_2} (m_1 \vec{x}_1 + m_2 \vec{x}_2) \quad (3)$$

We may now describe the distance between the two bodies with the following vector:

$$\vec{r} = |\vec{x}_1 - \vec{x}_2|$$

In line with Newton's universal law of gravitation, each body therefore experiences a force of attraction with a magnitude shown below:

$$F = \frac{Gm_1m_2}{r^2}$$

The net force on the system of two bodies—and therefore on the centre of mass—is equal to the sum of the forces of each body. Because the two forces are experienced in opposite directions to each other, the net force sums to zero:

$$F_{net} = F_{CoM} = \frac{Gm_1m_2}{r^2} - \frac{Gm_1m_2}{r^2} = 0$$

Applying Newton's second law of motion with our definition of the centre of mass from Equation (3):

$$F = ma$$

$$F_{net} = F_{CoM} = (m_1 + m_2) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \vec{R} = 0$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2} \vec{R} = 0$$

Therefore, relative to the inertial frame of reference, the centre of mass experiences no acceleration. Because of this, the motion of the bodies may be considered solely relative to the motion of the centre of mass. Using this, we may now draw a new coordinate system, taking the centre of mass itself as an origin for a coordinate system:

Figure 2: Centre-of-Mass Coordinate System

3.2 Reduction to a One-Body Problem

In this new coordinate system, the position vector of each body is now just the displacement vector from the centre of mass to that body. With this in mind, we will define a new vector $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$ as the movement from the centre of mass to the body one.

Utilising vector $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$, and with the centre of mass at the origin, the following equation may be written:

$$\frac{1}{m_1 + m_2} (m_1 \vec{\mathbf{B}} + m_2 \vec{\mathbf{x}}_2) = 0$$

Performing some rearranging:

$$m_1 \vec{\mathbf{B}} + m_2 \vec{\mathbf{x}}_2 = 0$$

$$m_1 \vec{\mathbf{B}} = -m_2 \vec{\mathbf{x}}_2$$

$$-\frac{m_1}{m_2} \vec{\mathbf{B}} = \vec{\mathbf{x}}_2$$

Therefore, in this new system, the displacement vector from the origin (centre of mass) to the second body is equal to $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$ multiplied by the ratio of the masses of the first and second bodies, multiplied by negative one:

$$\vec{\mathbf{x}}_2 = -\frac{m_1}{m_2} \vec{\mathbf{B}} \tag{4}$$

Because the masses are constant, Equation (4) tells us that the displacement vector of the second body is proportional to the displacement of the first body from the centre of mass ($\vec{\mathbf{B}}$), but multiplied by the ratio of the first mass to the second mass. The negative sign indicates that the body is in the opposite direction to the first body from the centre of mass. This is all in-line with our understanding of the definition of a centre of mass. Equation (4) is highly useful because it reveals that by knowing the motion of the first body relative to the centre of mass, the motion of the second body can also be calculated. In this way, the system has effectively been reduced

to that of a single body problem.

3.3 Establishment of an Acceleration Function

Now that the two bodies have been related in this manner, we will attempt to derive a formula for the acceleration of the first body. To do this, we will need to make use of the universal law of gravitation—Equation (1)—, expressing it in terms of our new quantities.

We may start by defining the absolute length of $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$ —or in other words the distance between the centre of mass and the first body—as b . By doing this, we can express the total distance between the two bodies as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} & b + \left(\frac{m_1}{m_2}\right)b \\ &= \left(\frac{m_2}{m_2}\right)b + \left(\frac{m_1}{m_2}\right)b \\ &= \left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{m_2}\right)b \end{aligned}$$

Now, we may express the force of gravitation attraction between the two bodies as:

$$F = \frac{Gm_1m_2}{\left(\left(\frac{m_1+m_2}{m_2}\right)b\right)^2} = \frac{Gm_1m_2}{\left(\frac{m_1+m_2}{m_2}\right)^2 b^2} \quad (5)$$

Finally, as the masses of both bodies are constant, we may now apply Newton's second law of motion in the form of Equation (2) to establish a formula for the acceleration of the vector $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$. To do this, we will denote the unit vector in the direction of $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$ as $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$. The direction of acceleration is negative with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$, as the body is accelerating in the direction of the centre of mass, towards the second body:

$$\vec{\mathbf{a}} = \frac{d^2}{dt^2}\vec{\mathbf{B}} = -\frac{F}{m_1}\hat{\mathbf{b}}$$

Substituting the new expression for the gravitational force (Equation (5)) and performing some simplification:

$$\begin{aligned} &= -\frac{Gm_1m_2}{m_1\left(\frac{m_1+m_2}{m_2}\right)^2 b^2}\hat{\mathbf{b}} = -\frac{Gm_2}{\left(\frac{m_1+m_2}{m_2}\right)^2 b^2}\hat{\mathbf{b}} \\ &= -\frac{Gm_2}{\frac{(m_1+m_2)^2}{m_2^2} b^2}\hat{\mathbf{b}} \\ &\vec{\mathbf{a}} = \frac{d^2}{dt^2}\vec{\mathbf{B}} = -\frac{Gm_2^3}{(m_1 + m_2)^2 b^2}\hat{\mathbf{b}} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

To reduce the complexity of this equation, the constants may be grouped together by defining:

$$K = \frac{Gm_2^3}{(m_1 + m_2)^2}$$

Now:

$$\vec{a} = \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \vec{B} = -\frac{K}{b^2} \hat{b} \quad (7)$$

3.4 Establishment of a Further Displacement-Velocity Relationship

Unfortunately, as we are currently unable to define a directly in terms of t , Equation (6) cannot simply be integrated. As a matter of fact, by reading more about the Two-Body Problem, I came to realise that due to the complexities of the system, simply creating an acceleration function in terms of time and integrating is not a practical solution to the problem. From here, I instead returned back to the system of vectors described earlier to attempt to establish further relationships that may be helpful in solving the problem.

As a first step, we can define the vector \hat{s} as the unit vector in the direction of $\frac{d}{dt} \hat{b}$, where n is some scale factor:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{b} = n \hat{s} \quad (8)$$

With this definition, the vector \hat{s} effectively represents the direction of the velocity of the body relative to the centre of mass of the system, as its direction is that of the rate of change of the vector in the direction of the displacement of the body from the centre of mass.

Let's now consider the unit vectors of \hat{b} and \hat{s} unit vectors in terms of their angles relative to the x-axis of the coordinate diagram. Defining θ as the angle between \hat{b} and the x-axis, because the magnitude \hat{b} in line with its definition as a unit vector, it may be described simply as:

Figure 3: Unit Vector Diagram

$$\hat{b} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta \end{pmatrix}$$

Let's now try to take the derivative of $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$ with its new definition:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \cos \theta \\ \frac{d}{dt} \sin \theta \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \\ \cos \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

Because θ is simply a scalar quantity, being just an angle, the rate of change of θ is also a scalar quantity. But as $\frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}}$ is still a vector quantity, for the above equation to hold true the vector $\begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}$ must be a vector in the direction of the rate of change of the vector $\vec{\mathbf{B}}$, or in other words a multiple of the vector $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \frac{d\theta}{dt} = n \hat{\mathbf{s}} \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

We can actually go a step further with this simplification by assessing the magnitude of the $\begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}$ vector:

$$\left| \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \right| = \sqrt{(-\sin \theta)^2 + \cos^2 \theta}$$

$$= \sqrt{\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta} = \sqrt{1} = 1$$

With a magnitude of 1, the vector $\begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}$ is itself a unit vector, meaning that it must equal $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ itself:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} = \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \tag{9}$$

This equation tells us that the rate of change of the direction of the first body from the centre of mass is equal to the direction of its velocity, multiplied by the rate of change of the angle of the body from the x-axis. This is difficult to visualise, but it will help us momentarily in developing more mathematical relationships.

We can also take the derivative of $\begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} = \hat{\mathbf{s}}$ itself:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} &= \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{d}{dt} \sin \theta \\ \frac{d}{dt} \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \\ -\sin \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta \end{pmatrix} \frac{d\theta}{dt} = -\hat{\mathbf{b}} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the following equation is also true:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} = -\frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} \tag{10}$$

Equation (10) is easier to understand. It tells us that the velocity vector of the body (of which $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ is the unit vector) is constantly bending in the direction of the centre of mass $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$. This aligns with our understanding of the forces involved.

At all times, the body is being accelerated in the direction of the centre of mass in accordance with Newton's principles. As it moves in space, the direction of this acceleration changes such that it is always towards the centre of mass. With the direction of its acceleration changing, the direction of the body's velocity also changes in that direction. Because the $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$ vector is pointing from the centre of mass to the body, a negative sign is present in the equation to instead have the vector be pointed from the body to the centre of mass.

This movement of the velocity vector is proportional to the rate of change of the angle between the body and the x-axis. In other words, it's proportional to the angular velocity of the body. If the body is closer to the centre of mass, as it moves its relative angle will be changing faster, and so the direction of its velocity must also change faster for it to maintain an orbit. When further away, the direction of the velocity will not need to change as fast.

3.5 Establishment of A Mathematical Velocity Function

Now that we have established some further relationships between the displacement and velocity vectors, let's attempt to establish a velocity function by taking the derivative of the displacement vector:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{v} &= n\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \frac{d}{dt}\vec{\mathbf{B}} \\ &= \frac{d}{dt}(b\hat{\mathbf{b}}) = \frac{db}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{b}}}{dt}b\end{aligned}$$

Now applying the relationship from Equation (9):

$$\vec{v} = \frac{db}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{b}} + b\frac{d\theta}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{s}} \quad (11)$$

3.6 Derivation of an Alternative Acceleration Function

Equation (11) is a function of the velocity of body one. By taking the derivative of this function with respect to time, we can produce an alternative acceleration function, and then compare that with our original function from Equation (7):

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{a} &= \frac{d}{dt}\vec{v} = \frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{db}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{b}} + b\frac{d\theta}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{s}}\right) \\ &= \frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{db}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{b}}\right) + \frac{d}{dt}\left(b\frac{d\theta}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{s}}\right)\end{aligned}$$

Now applying the chain rule for both derivatives, and doing so twice within second term:

$$= \left(\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{b}}}{dt} \right) + \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} + b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{s}}}{dt} + \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \right) \right)$$

Let's now apply the relationship from Equation (9) to the $\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{b}}}{dt}$ term, and the one in Equation (10) to the $\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{s}}}{dt}$ term:

$$= \left(\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \right) + \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} + b \left(-\frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \right) \right)$$

And now we can simplify and organise:

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} + \frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{s}} + b \left(-\frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \right) \\ &= \frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + 2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) \hat{\mathbf{s}} + b \left(-\left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \right) \\ &= \frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{b}} + 2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) \hat{\mathbf{s}} - b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 \hat{\mathbf{b}} + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \hat{\mathbf{s}} \\ &= \left(\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} - b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 \right) \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \left(2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \right) \hat{\mathbf{s}} \end{aligned}$$

And thus:

$$\vec{\mathbf{a}} = \left(\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} - b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 \right) \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \left(2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \right) \hat{\mathbf{s}} \quad (12)$$

To establish the earlier acceleration function (Equation (7)), we looked directly at the gravitational force of attraction experienced by the bodies that generates this acceleration. What we have just done now with Equation (12) is an alternative approach, focusing instead on the movement and position of the body in vector space. Both of these functions describe the acceleration vector of the body, but they do so with different terms. This allows us to equate them, developing a connection between the gravitational force and positional vectors.

3.7 Comparison Between Acceleration Functions

Let's now equate Equation (12)'s acceleration function with the acceleration function established earlier in Equation (7).

$$\vec{\mathbf{a}} = -\frac{K}{b^2} \hat{\mathbf{b}} = \left(\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} - b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 \right) \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \left(2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \right) \hat{\mathbf{s}}$$

By comparing the coefficients for the $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$ term in both equations, we can extract two interesting relationships:

$$\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} - b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 = -\frac{K}{b^2} \quad (13)$$

$$2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Taking a closer look at Equation (14), we notice that it closely resembles the derivative of $b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt}$ shown below:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) = 2b \frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} + b^2 \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} = b \left(2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \right)$$

As can be seen above, Equation (14), when multiplied by b , is equal to the derivative of $b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt}$. Remembering that this quantity is equal to 0 (also from Equation (14)), we can therefore conclude that:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) = b \left(2 \left(\frac{db}{dt} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) + b \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} \right) = b \times 0$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) = 0$$

If its derivative is equal to zero, then the quantity $b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt}$ (defined below as L) must be a constant:

$$L = b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

A simple rearrangement also tells us that:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{L}{b^2} \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) is another big development in our understanding of the system. It tells us that the rate of change of the angle between the body and the x-axis, or in the other words the angular velocity of the body is inversely proportional to the square of the distance between the body and the centre of mass. A body further away from the centre of mass with orbit about the centre of mass with a slower angular velocity. This is intuitive as at a further distance from the centre of mass, the same angle will constitute a longer arc in an orbit about the centre of mass.

3.8 Definition of Final Variables

With a clear relationship between the magnitude of the distance between the body (b) and the centre of mass, and the angle from the x-axis to the centre of mass (θ), we may now attempt to produce an expression for b in terms of θ .

Achieving this expression involves taking a series of derivatives. To be able to do this, several substitutions must be made. The reasoning behind the choice of these specific variables to be used in the substitution is not immediately obvious, and in fact does not become clear until most of the differentiation and algebraic manipulation has been performed. Because of this, for these steps in the process I directly followed the workings of other mathematicians who have solved this problem before.³

³Kansas State University. (2011). The Two-Body Problem. <https://www.math.ksu.edu/~dbski/writings/twobody.pdf>

We have already defined the constants:

$$K = \frac{Gm_2^3}{(m_1 + m_2)^2} \quad (16)$$

and:

$$L = b^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} \quad (17)$$

From this, let us define a new variable u :

$$u = \frac{L^2}{Kb} \quad (18)$$

Looking at u , we can see that:

$$b = \frac{L^2}{Ku} \quad (19)$$

We also already established in Equation (15) that:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{L}{b^2}$$

Applying our definition of b from Equation (19):

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{L}{b^2} = \frac{L}{\left(\frac{L^2}{Ku}\right)^2} = \frac{LK^2u^2}{L^4} = \frac{K^2u^2}{L^3}$$

Thus:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{K^2u^2}{L^3} \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) is difficult to intuitively understand, but as we begin deriving a displacement function below, its importance as a substituted variable will become clear.

3.9 Derivation of a Displacement Function in Terms of θ

At last all of the required variables have been defined. Let's now begin the final series of derivations by taking the derivative of b , applying our definition of b from Equation (19). To be clear, this b is the scalar distance between the centre of mass and body one, not a vector, and so this derivative is not a velocity function, but instead a scalar speed function with no direction.

$$\frac{db}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{L^2}{Ku} \right)$$

To handle this derivative, we will derive implicitly with respect to θ :

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{L^2}{Ku} \right) = \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\frac{L^2}{Ku} \right) \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

L and K are both constants as established. We are not able to express u in terms of θ , and so we will need to differentiate implicitly again:

$$\frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\frac{L^2}{Ku} \right) \frac{d\theta}{dt} = \left(-\frac{L^2}{Ku^2} \frac{du}{d\theta} \right) \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

We can now substitute our expression for $\frac{d\theta}{dt}$ from Equation (20):

$$\begin{aligned} \left(-\frac{L^2}{Ku^2} \frac{du}{d\theta} \right) \frac{d\theta}{dt} &= \left(-\frac{L^2}{Ku^2} \frac{du}{d\theta} \right) \left(\frac{K^2 u^2}{L^3} \right) \\ &= \left(-\frac{L^2 K^2 u^2}{Ku^2 L^3} \right) \frac{du}{d\theta} \\ &= -\frac{K}{L} \frac{du}{d\theta} \end{aligned}$$

And thus:

$$\frac{db}{dt} = -\frac{K}{L} \frac{du}{d\theta} \tag{21}$$

Let's now take the second derivative, again deriving implicitly with respect to time:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} &= \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{db}{dt} \right) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{K}{L} \frac{du}{d\theta} \right) \\ &= \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(-\frac{K}{L} \frac{du}{d\theta} \right) \frac{d\theta}{dt} \\ &= -\frac{K}{L} \frac{d^2 u}{d\theta^2} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \end{aligned}$$

Once again we can substitute the expression for $\frac{d\theta}{dt}$ from Equation (20):

$$\begin{aligned} &= -\frac{K}{L} \frac{d^2 u}{d\theta^2} \left(\frac{K^2 u^2}{L^3} \right) \\ &= -\frac{K^3 u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2 u}{d\theta^2} \end{aligned}$$

Thus:

$$\frac{d^2 b}{dt^2} = -\frac{K^3 u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2 u}{d\theta^2} \tag{22}$$

The exact implications of Equation (22) are difficult to express. It should be noted that as b is a scalar value, this is not a vector acceleration function. Instead, this function expresses the rate of change of the scalar speed of the distance between the centre of mass and body one. Although the equation itself is not entirely helpful, we have seen this $\frac{d^2b}{dt^2}$ term before in the second acceleration function (Equation (12)). With it now defined in terms of our new variables, let's return to the first interesting relationship realised when the two acceleration functions were compared earlier, expressed as Equation (13) which has been shown again below:

$$\frac{d^2b}{dt^2} - b \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 = -\frac{K}{b^2}$$

Now substituting our new expressions from Equation (22), Equation (19) and Equation (20):

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \left(\frac{L^2}{Ku} \right) \left(\frac{K^2u^2}{L^3} \right)^2 &= -\frac{K}{b^2} \\ &= -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \frac{L^2}{Ku} \frac{K^4u^4}{L^6} \\ &= -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \frac{K^3u^3}{L^4} \end{aligned}$$

And so:

$$= -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \frac{K^3u^3}{L^4} = -\frac{K}{b^2}$$

Now we can against substitute the expression from Equation (19) for the b^2 term on the right-hand-side of the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} &= -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \frac{K^3u^3}{L^4} = -\frac{K}{\left(\frac{L^2}{Ku} \right)^2} \\ &= -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \frac{K^3u^3}{L^4} = -K \times \left(\frac{Ku}{L^2} \right)^2 \\ &= -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} - \frac{K^3u^3}{L^4} = -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \end{aligned}$$

Factoring out and dividing by the common $-\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4}$ term:

$$= \left(-\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \right) \frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} + \left(-\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4} \right) u = -\frac{K^3u^2}{L^4}$$

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} + u = 1 \tag{23}$$

Through my research, I came to learn that Equation (23) is an example of a non-homogeneous second-order linear differential equation.⁴ While it is possible to solve this equation by hand, producing an expression for u as a function of θ , this process is highly complex and beyond the scope of the Mathematics: Analysis and Approaches course. Instead, the problem has been processed by the Wolfram Alpha online mathematics engine.⁵

Equation (23) has the following general solution where c_1 and c_2 are constants determined by the initial conditions of the bodies and system:

$$u = u(\theta) = c_2 \sin \theta + c_1 \cos \theta + 1 \quad (24)$$

From further reading, I learnt that we can actually reduce the complexity of this equation, representing the sum of these two sinusoidal functions as a single sinusoidal function, by employing a harmonic trigonometric identity. This has been done below:

First, let's define a singular function which is equal to the sum of the two functions where e and θ_0 are both constants. It should be noted that the e here is not equivalent Euler's number. The reasoning behind the choice of the letter e will become clear once this identity has been employed.

$$e \cos(\theta + \theta_0) = c_2 \sin \theta + c_1 \cos \theta$$

Let's now expand $e \cos(\theta + \theta_0)$ with the compound angle identity:

$$e \cos(\theta + \theta_0) = e(\cos \theta \cos \theta_0 - \sin \theta \sin \theta_0) = e \cos \theta \cos \theta_0 - e \sin \theta \sin \theta_0$$

We can now equate the coefficients from Equation (24) to the extra cos and sin terms:

$$c_2 \sin \theta + c_1 \cos \theta = (e \cos \theta_0) \cos \theta + (-e \sin \theta_0) \sin \theta$$

$$c_1 = e \cos \theta_0$$

$$c_2 = -e \sin \theta_0$$

From here, we can define θ_0 in terms of c_1 and c_2 by dividing the two equations:

$$\frac{c_2}{c_1} = \frac{-e \sin \theta_0}{e \cos \theta_0} = -\frac{\sin \theta_0}{\cos \theta_0} = \tan \theta_0$$

⁴Strang, G., & Herman, E. (2016, July 11). 17.2: Nonhomogeneous Linear Equations. Mathematics LibreTexts. [https://math.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Calculus/Calculus_\(OpenStax\)/17%3A_Second-Order_Differential_Equations/17.02%3A_Nonhomogeneous_Linear_Equations](https://math.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Calculus/Calculus_(OpenStax)/17%3A_Second-Order_Differential_Equations/17.02%3A_Nonhomogeneous_Linear_Equations)

⁵Wolfram Alpha. (2023). Wolfram—Alpha: Making the world's knowledge computable. Wolframalpha.com. <https://www.wolframalpha.com/>

$$\theta_0 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{c_2}{c_1} \right)$$

Next, by squaring and adding the two equations, we can define e in terms of c_1 and c_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} c_1^2 + c_2^2 &= (e \cos \theta_0)^2 + (-e \sin \theta_0)^2 \\ &= e^2 \cos^2 \theta_0 + e^2 \sin^2 \theta_0 \\ &= e^2 (\cos^2 \theta_0 + \sin^2 \theta_0) = e^2(1) \\ c_1^2 + c_2^2 &= e^2 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, when expressed in terms of c_1 and c_2 , $e \cos(\theta + \theta_0)$ may be written as follows:

$$\left(\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2} \right) \cos \left(\theta - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{c_2}{c_1} \right) \right)$$

Returning to Equation (24), by defining:

$$\begin{aligned} e &= \sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2} \\ \theta_0 &= \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{c_2}{c_1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

We may rewrite Equation(24) as follows, where e and θ_0 are also constants determined by the initial conditions of the bodies and system:

$$u = u(\theta) = 1 + e \cos(\theta - \theta_0) \tag{25}$$

By applying this new expression for u to Equation (19), we are able to express the scalar distance (b) between the centre of mass of the system and body one in terms of the angle between the body and the x-axis (θ):

$$b = \frac{L^2}{Ku} = \frac{L^2}{K(1 + e \cos(\theta - \theta_0))} \tag{26}$$

As it turns out, remembering that L and K are constants, this equation actually also describes the polar equation of a conic section focused at the origin with an eccentricity of e .

3.10 Conic Sections

A conic section is the two-dimensional shape formed by the intersection between a three-dimensional double cone and a two-dimensional plane. Depending on the angle between which the cone and plane intersect, the resulting shape may be either a circle, ellipses, parabola or hyperbola.

Figure 4: Conic Sections (ck-12.org)

A conic section may be defined with reference to a singular point referred to as the ‘focus’, and a straight line that does not contain the focus referred to as the ‘directrix’. In this definition, the conic section is described as “the locus of points for each of which the distance to the focus divided by the distance to the directrix is a fixed positive constant”⁶. This constant is the eccentricity of the curve.

The above definition has been illustrated algebraically in the below polar equation, where r is the distance from a given point on curve to the focus, the line $x = p$ is the directrix, and the positive constant is e , the eccentricity of the curve:

$$r = \frac{ep}{(1 + \cos \theta)}$$

When $e = 0$, the conic section will form a perfect circle, when $0 < e < 1$, it will form an ellipse, when $e = 1$, a parabola is formed, and when $e > 1$ a hyperbola is formed.⁷ In this sense, the eccentricity value effectively describes the circularity of the curve:

Figure 5: Eccentricity of a Conic Section (mathsisfun.com)

Returning to Equation (26), the orbit of body one about the centre of mass is described in terms of the distance (b) between the body and the centre of mass at each angle (θ).

⁶Pierce, R. (2021). Conic Sections. MathsisFun. <https://www.mathsisfun.com/geometry/conic-sections.html>

⁷Pierce, R. (2021b). Eccentricity. MathsisFun. <https://www.mathsisfun.com/geometry/eccentricity.html>

As mentioned earlier, the eccentricity, e , is a constant determined by the initial conditions of the system, namely the masses and velocities of both bodies. It should also be remembered that the relative position of body two is directly related to that of body one, as described in Equation (4).

If $0 < e < 1$, then the bodies will form a stable elliptical orbit about the centre of mass relative to the inertial frame of reference. If $e \geq 1$, the gravitational force is insufficient to establish an orbit between the bodies at their velocities, and so the bodies will follow a parabolic or hyperbolic path, ultimately moving away from each other.

As such, Equation (26) is a complete mathematical model of the motion of a body in a closed two-body system.

3.11 Further Extension

Although Equation (26) is a solution to the two-body problem, it still contains constants which have not been numerically defined (L , e and θ_0). From further reading, I came to learn that it is possible to define each of these constants in terms of the initial conditions of the system—namely the initial positions and initial velocities of each of the bodies.⁸ For the purpose of this investigation however, this process will not be shown, as it involves a considerable amount of further mathematical working and sits outside of the paper's aim.

4 Real-Life Application and Modelling

Having reached an equation that describes the orbit of the bodies in a two-body system, I decided to attempt to apply it to a real two-body system.

4.1 The Sirius System

Sirius is a star system approximately 8.6 light years away from Earth. It is the brightest star visible in the night sky.⁹

⁸Kansas State University. (2011). The Two-Body Problem. <https://www.math.ksu.edu/~dbski/writings/twobody.pdf>

⁹Jones, T. (2023). Sirius is the Brightest Star in the Sky. AstroBackyard — Astrophotography Tips and Tutorials. <https://astrobackyard.com/sirius-star/>

Figure 6: Sirius in the Night Sky (astrobackyard.com)

Interestingly, the system actually consists of two stars (Sirius A and Sirius B) in a binary orbit. Sirius A is a larger main sequence star with a mass approximately twice that of the Sun. Sirius B, on the other hand, is a smaller white dwarf star with a mass roughly equal to that of the Sun. Both stars orbit about the centre of mass of their two-body system in stable orbits.

This means that it is possible to describe and model the orbits of Sirius A and Sirius B using our equations.

4.2 Applying the Model

To model the system, I used the online graphing calculator Desmos, plotting Equation (26) as a polar equation. The masses of both stars were found online¹⁰ and converted from solar masses to kilograms, and the Gravitational Constant (G) was taken from the IB Physics Data Booklet, allowing the constant K to be calculated:

$$K = \frac{Gm_2^3}{(m_1 + m_2)^2} = \frac{6.81 \times 10^{-11} \times (1.018 \times 1.989 \times 10^{30})^3}{(2.063 \times 1.989 \times 10^{30} + 1.018 \times 1.989 \times 10^{30})^2} \approx 1.474 \times 10^{19} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

The eccentricity (e) was also found online—as mentioned earlier it is possible to calculate this from initial conditions, but for the purpose of this investigation that has not been done.

$$e = 0.59142$$

Observing the fact that $0 < e < 1$, we can already guess that the bodies will experience stable, elliptical orbits about the centre of mass.

The θ_0 term, which describes the angle of the orbits relative to a coordinate plane, was set to equal π , allowing the orbits to sit in-line with the x-axis.

Finally, the value of L was estimated. Because L^2 is proportional to b (Equation (26)), this value actually only

¹⁰Wikipedia Contributors. (2019, September 4). Sirius. Wikipedia; Wikimedia Foundation. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sirius>

changes the size of the orbits, not their shapes or relative positions.

With all of these values defined, the conic section describing body one's orbit was drawn:

$$b_1 = \frac{L^2}{K(1 + e \cos(\theta - \theta_0))}$$

On the same graph, the conic section describing body two's orbit was also drawn, using the principle of the relationship described in Equation (4):

$$b_2 = \left(-\frac{m_1}{m_2}\right) b_1 = \left(-\frac{m_1}{m_2}\right) \frac{L^2}{K(1 + e \cos(\theta - \theta_0))}$$

The below Figure 7 presents the results of this graphing:

Figure 7: The Binary Orbits of Sirius A and Sirius B

As can be seen above, both stars experience elliptical orbits. As has been done throughout this paper, the coordinate system was defined such that the centre of mass sits at the origin. In line with the definition of the centre of mass, this position is closer to Sirius A—the more massive star—than Sirius B.

From this graph we can note some interesting details. Firstly, the more massive Sirius A experiences a shorter orbit when compared with the less massive Sirius B. This aligns with our understanding of the involved forces. Being more massive, the same gravitational force will generate less acceleration upon Sirius A, and so its movement is comparatively lower.

Additionally, with the negative relationship between the position of Sirius A and Sirius B (Equation (4)), the stars will always directly oppose each other, as they are doing in the position shown in Figure 7.

5 Conclusion

Over the course of this investigation, the nature of the forces of gravitational attraction between two bodies and their influences on the motion of the bodies was explored. By describing the system in terms of the vector positions of the bodies relative to a coordinate plane, I was able to derive and develop mathematical relationships between the spacial properties of the bodies. The manipulation of these relationships culminated in Equation (26), where the motion of the bodies was described by the polar equation of a conic section.

This vector-based approach proved useful in looking at the problem from a mathematical-standpoint, though it quickly quite highly complex as vectors were manipulated in unique and elaborate ways. Additionally, while graphs and diagrams were able to be used to illustrate some relationships, many values and equations were arbitrary and difficult to conceptually understand. Nevertheless, the success of this investigation highlights the potency of mathematics as a tool to describe reality.